

R6.1.1
ASAP
Visual Identity

Co-funded by
the European Union

ACAD

proposta icone per sezione

School kids

School teachers

Parents

Title

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FONT: TestMe

INDICAZIONI PER LA FORMATTAZIONE:

- allineato a sinistra, sbandierato
- corpo del testo 12/14 punti
- interlinea 1.5
- Meglio evitare trattino-a capo-
- NO testo in colonne
- NO corsivi o sottolineati
- OK grassetto
- evitare maiuscolo
- ok elenchi puntati
- meglio punto e a capo invece che punto e di seguito
- soprattutto se il punto cade alla fine della riga
- evitare sfondo bianco, meglio crema/panna

TITLE

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ASAP

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